

Pipeline for the 3D Shape and Cell Proliferation Analysis in a Regenerating Axolotl Humerus

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This document describes in detail the process followed in Fiji [1], MATLAB [2] and STARDIST-3D [3] to obtain the results shown in the main study¹. It is written as a step-by-step tutorial aimed at inexperienced users of these software. The scripts mentioned here are also provided as supplementary material and contain self-explanatory annotations of their contents². A few example input files required to run the scripts discussed in this text are provided. The dataset of .czi images and additional intermediate files used in the main study are available upon reasonable request to Sandra J. Shefelbine (s.shefelbine@northeastern.edu).

The data analysis pipeline presented here is based on the multiscale data analysis methodology recently published by our group [4]. We process 3D image stacks showing axolotl elbows stained with click-it ready AHA and EdU molecules, which allow us to quantify bone rudiment shape and cell proliferation, respectively. The experimental methods are described in the main study. These resulted in two groups of forelimbs: (1) a control group in which animals were injected with DMSO and forelimbs regenerated under normal conditions, and (2) a group in which animals were injected with GSK1016790A, a TRPV4 agonist, resulting in impaired TRPV4 channels in cell membranes and, consequently, regenerating forelimbs were unable to respond to mechanical stimuli.

Below is a representative slice of one of the DMSO image stacks processed. Here, the first channel (left) shows the AHA staining in green, and the second channel (right) shows the EdU staining in red. Some image stacks have the staining colors inverted.

¹ A preprint version of the study is available on bioRxiv: <https://doi.org/10.1101/2021.08.28.458034>

² All versions of this tutorial and the associated files are available on Zenodo: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5591984>

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If you find typos or errors in this tutorial, or have suggestions for improvement, please email them to Ester Comellas at ester.comellas@upc.edu.

Overview of the data analysis pipeline

Figure 1 below (extracted from the main study) outlines the data analysis methodology followed to quantify the shape of the regenerated axolotl humeri obtained in the experiments.

Figure 1. Complete workflow of the experimental data analysis using an exemplary control limb.

Processing of an original image stack

This section corresponds to Fig 1A-D.

Before starting, those without a background in microscopy image analysis are strongly encouraged to watch the following iBiology lecture about digital image analysis by Nico Stuurman: <https://www.ibiology.org/talks/digital-image-analysis/>

The iBiology website provides numerous lectures which are also a good introduction to microscopy basics. Our images are taken with a light sheet fluorescence microscope. You might find it useful to watch the Fluorescence Microscopy lectures available here: <https://www.ibiology.org/online-biology-courses/short-microscopy-series/>

Step 1. Import the image stack into Fiji.

- Import the .czi file by dragging and dropping the file on the Fiji.

Tips: an alternative to using virtual stack when the image is too large for Fiji to load, is to assign more memory, if your computer has the capacity. Type *Memory* in the search window of the tool bar and select *Memory & Threads* and click on *Run*. Change the maximum memory value. As a rule of thumb, select about 75% of your total RAM capacity.

Also, all commands can be found by typing the name into the search bar, instead of navigating through menus.

It is useful to keep a window open to keep track of the memory usage while you work in Fiji. Go to (*Plugins > Utilities > Monitor Memory...*) If you double-click on the Memory window, you might see the usage go down. This activates the garbage collector, freeing memory that is not being used.

Take note of the pixel resolution (x, y and z values). We might need this later. Certain operations in Fiji a remove the resolution properties of the stack. If you did not display metadata with the import or you want to check at any time the pixel resolution, you will find it in (*Image > Properties*).

Key	Value
Positions Series 1 #347	0
Positions Series 1 #348	0
Positions Series 1 #349	0
Positions Series 1 #350	0
Positions Series 1 #351	0
Positions Series 1 #352	0
Positions Series 1 #353	0
Positions Series 1 #354	0
Positions Series 1 #355	0
Positions Series 1 #356	0
Positions Series 1 #357	0
Positions Series 1 #358	0
Scaling Distance Id #1	X
Scaling Distance Id #2	Y
Scaling Distance Id #3	Z
Scaling Distance Value #1	9.1535801334752513e-007
Scaling Distance Value #2	9.1535801334752513e-007
Scaling Distance Value #3	4.9453993555402829e-006
Version #1	1.0

The image may appear very dark. To adjust the visualization, go to (*Image > Adjust > Brightness/Contrast*) and click on *Auto* in the window that appeared.

Tip: You might need to scroll to a central slice in the stack for the auto-adjustment to work better. You can also set the limits of the display range manually in *Set*. **NEVER** click on *Apply* or the limits set will be permanently applied on the image stack, modifying the intensity of the data we want to analyze.

Tip: Save the stack as a .tif file. Most of Fiji’s operations do not have an “undo” option, so it is good practice to save files (*File* > *Save As...* > *Tiff...*) at each step and work always on duplicate copies (*Image* > *Duplicate...*).

Important Tip: All Fiji operations can be executed either through the Graphical User Interface (e.g. *Image* > *Duplicate...*) or via commands in the Interactive Interpreter (shown in the image to the right). To access the Interactive Interpreter, go to (*Plugins* > *Macros* > *Interactive Interpreter...*). The advantage of using the Interactive Interpreter is that we can keep track of the exact processing steps applied to each image. It is good scientific practice to note down key information in a separate text file (e.g. rotation angle applied, cropping size and position, etc.) for each image stack processed such that the procedure can be reproduced as exactly as possible in the future.

A useful plugin that complements the Interactive Interpreter is the Recorder (*Plugins* > *Macros* > *Recorder...*). If you are unsure of the written form of a specific command you want to apply via the Interactive Interpreter (or in a macro you are creating), you can first apply it on a test image using the standard GUI and the corresponding written command is shown in the Recorder window.

Step 2. Align and crop the image stack along the proximodistal axis of the humerus.

- If the humerus is in the bottom part of the image, flip the image stack upside down: (*Image* › *Transform* › *Flip Vertically...*) or `[run("Flip Vertically", "stack");]`.

Important note: After processing all limbs, we realized flipping results in mirroring of the limbs. We recommend rotating the image stack rather than flipping to align the humerus. Flipping should be reserved exclusively to mirror all right limbs to be able to process them all as left limbs (with the same relative position in 3D space of radius and ulna), or vice versa.

- Rotate the image stack: (*Image* › *Transform* › *Rotate...*) or `[run("Rotate...", "angle=54 grid=0 interpolation=Bicubic stack");]` to vertically align the humerus' proximodistal axis. Activate *Preview* and adjust the angle until the humerus bone rudiment is vertical. Grid lines will help with the adjustment. We use a bicubic interpolation and choose to enlarge the image to keep as much humerus as possible. We use the AHA channel because the bone rudiment geometry is clearer, and rotate the stack 54 degrees. Click on Yes to process the whole stack.

Tip: Here, the GUI is preferred over the Interactive Interpreter because it allows to adjust the rotation angle thanks to the "Preview" function. Do keep note of the rotation angle applied on each image stack.

Tip: Once you have decided the rotation angle to apply, change grid lines to zero before clicking on "Ok" to apply the rotation to the whole image stack. Sometimes a glitch in Fiji results in the new rotated image permanently incorporating the grid into the image stack.

- Crop the image stack to reduce file size and remove empty corners due to the rotation applied. We must ensure that the largest amount of humerus shaft is included in the crop, in addition to the radius and ulna. In the example below, we use a rectangle with top left corner at position (820, 572), width of 1116 and height of 1572 (values given in "pixels"). To apply the crop, use the "Duplicate" command. Here, you can also remove slices from the beginning and end of the stack in which there are no bone rudiments (make sure to adjust the brightness and contrast to aid in this decision).

The top limit is dictated by the uppermost cross-section of the humerus that is complete (i.e., not affected by the top "empty corners" the rotation has created).

Make the rectangle as narrow as possible, while containing the complete elbow joint. Scroll through the stack to ensure all the humerus is

The rectangle width and the rectangle's lower limit will likely be dictated by the lower left "empty corner".

Tip: Remember to note down the size and position of the crop applied; in case we must replicate this in the future. The Recorder is a useful tool for this.

- It is a good idea to save the resulting stack, if you have not done so yet. Now we can split the channels (*Image > Color > Split Channels*; or import the saved stack and click on *split channels* in the importer window). We did not split channels until now, to make it easier to apply the exact same rectangle for cropping both channels.

Step 3. Segmentation of the bone rudiments: create the masks.

The outcome of the segmentation will depend greatly on the person doing the segmentation. It is important that a same person performs it and is consistent throughout the process, particularly if several samples are to be processed and compared. To ensure results were as consistent as possible, we selected 6 DMSO and 6 GSK limbs, had two researchers segment them separately, and verified that difference between results was within a 10% variation. We used the 3D shape analysis as well as the whole histogram for comparison.

- Open the AHA channel in the Segmentation Editor (*Plugins* › *Segmentation* › *Segmentation Editor*) to create the mask. Adjust the *Brightness & Contrast* to help distinguish better the outline of the bone rudiment. Note down the minimum and maximum values selected to use the exact same *Brightness & Contrast* setting with the three bone rudiments of a same image stack.

Tip: Switching the visualization from colored to grayscale might also help: (*Image* › *Lookup Tables* › *Grays*) or `[run("Grays");]`.

Here we include a summary and tips on how we segmented the bone rudiment, but do check out the ImageJ [5] documentation for more comprehensive instructions: https://imagej.net/Segmentation_Editor.

Use the “bean” icon to draw the outline of the humerus. Then, scroll several slices and draw again. Then, click on “I” (interpolate) to generate shapes in the slices in between. The 3D checkbox should be on.

“T” (threshold) refines the selected area based on a locally adjusted threshold. “O” (open) and “C” (close) applies the corresponding kernels to the selection and can be used for smoothing (see video in documentation, minutes 0:46 and 1:25.).

Then, add the shapes as mask. Make sure to check “3d” so all slices are added.

A new window with the file extension renamed “.labels” will appear with the masks in each slice.

If the interpolation didn't work out well, you can add/remove parts of the mask. Just draw new shapes and click the "+" or "-" button. However, it is better if one anticipates this and manually draws outlines in strategic slices, for example the one with the most downward position of the tip.

Tip: Press the "shift" key to draw separate shapes in a same slice. The software is able to interpolate between one shape in a slice and two shapes in a slice several slices beyond.

Also, it's better to use the interpolation function smartly than to segment each slice manually. In manual segmentation of consecutive stacks, we can't draw the shapes exactly in the same position as before. So, our 3D surface will not be as smooth and look "uneven":

- Once you're happy with the results, save the "labels" stack generated by the Segmentation Editor. This is our mask. It should be an 8-bit image stack in which the background has intensity value of zero and the bone rudiment mask has intensity value of one.

Tip: You can quickly check this by hovering your mouse pointer over the image and reading the intensity value displayed in the Fiji toolbar for the pixel below your pointer.

- Repeat the process for the other two bone rudiments using the same initial image stack and *Brightness & Contrast* settings.

Step 4. Segmentation of the bone rudiments: create the 3D surface files.

- To convert it to a 3D surface, open each image stack of masks in the 3D Viewer plugin [6]. Then export the surface as an .stl. First, convert the volume to a surface (*Edit > Display As... > Surface*) and then export (*File > Export Surfaces... > STL (binary)*). It doesn't really matter if you choose ASCII or binary, they will contain the exact same information. A binary file occupies less space and is preferable.

Tip: If your 3D volume is "squashed", the pixel resolution was probably lost at some point in this process. Check the properties of the image stack with the mask and update the values (we took note of them at the beginning when we looked at the metadata of the .czi file).

- For data analysis purposes, we will use this stack of masks without further modification. However, for visualization purposes, we can smooth the surface so the slices are not visible. For that, we use MeshLab [7]. Open the .stl file, clicking on *Unify Duplicated vertices*.

- We then reduce the file size and smooth out the surface by simplify the mesh using Clustering Decimation (*Filters > Remeshing, Simplification and Reconstruction > Simplification: Clustering Decimation*) with the following properties:

- We can further smooth the surface using HC Laplacian smoothing. We can repeatedly apply these two filters in succession, until we get a nice shape for visualization.

This process has modified the volume and cross-sections that we just segmented, this is the reason why we choose not to use the simplified surface for our analysis, to minimize unnecessary manipulation of our data.

Step 5. Apply the bone rudiment masks on the aligned and cropped image stack.

There are several ways of masking the aligned and cropped image stack, which we split into two separate channels. Here we explain two.

Option 1. Masking using the Image Calculator in Fiji.

- Open the stack containing the mask, and the stack with the image you want to crop. They should both be vertically aligned and cropped in exactly the same manner so that the overlay will coincide. The number of slices should also correspond for both.

Important tips: Ensure that your 8-bit mask has “0” intensity pixels in the background and “1” intensity pixels in the mask. This is easy to check by hovering the mouse pointer on the image and reading the value in the Fiji tool bar. This is important because otherwise the resulting masked image stack will be an 8-bit file instead of a 16-bit one. Also, the image stack we will crop should still be a 16-bit image! If this changed, we must go back and redo the processing correctly to ensure we do not lose this information.

- Use the Image Calculator (*Process > Image Calculator*) to multiply the two image stacks.

Tip: duplicate and rename each stack before applying the calculator.

Option 2. Masking using a macro.

- Alternatively, you can use the custom-made ImageJ macro “masking_macro.ijm” provided with the supplementary material. This macro automatizes the masking procedure described above. Open the file with ImageJ (drag and drop, or double click on the file in your system browser) and click on Run. Then follow the instructions in the pop-up windows.

Tip: If you mistakenly created a mask with value=255 instead of value=1, you can still run this masking macro successfully by uncommenting line 13 of the script.

For both options,

- Save the resulting image stack. Ensure it is a 16-bit image stack.
- Repeat the process for the two channels of each bone rudiment.

Step 6. Obtain the alignment matrix based on a PCA of the humerus.

To facilitate the shape analysis of the humeri, we use the tool in BoneJ [8] to determine the three orthogonal principal axes of the bone rudiment and the rotation matrix needed to align these axes (and the humerus surface) with the x, y and z axes of the image.

- Open the image stack of the humerus mask and go to the Moments of Inertia tool in BoneJ (*Plugins > BoneJ > Moments of Inertia*). Change the values of the Bone Min and Bone Max as needed. Given that our bone is a mask with intensity value of “1”, we introduce “1” for both.

- Save the contents of the Log window as a .txt file by selecting the window and (*File* \triangleright *Save As...*).

Either the “Original Rotation Matrix (Source \rightarrow Target)” or the “Corrected Z-flipping Reflected the rotation matrix Rotation Matrix (Source \rightarrow Target)” will be used to align the surface contained in the stl file created in Step 4 when we import it into MATLAB for the 3D shape analysis.

An additional step. Creating a histogram of a 16-bit image stack.

To ensure the original intensity distribution is not inadvertently modified, it is good practice to check our image stacks remain as 16-bit image files, and that they have reasonable histograms. We expect all our histograms to have a right-skewed distribution. An edge peak distribution or a comb distribution would indicate that our intensity values have been permanently modified and we must avoid this at all costs. Below are representative examples of these histogram distributions³.

The histogram available in Fiji within the *Brightness & Contrast* window averages intensity data into 256 ($=2^8$) bins and, therefore, does not display the true histogram, which should have 65536 ($=2^{16}$) bins.

An option is to go to (*Analyze > Histogram*) while holding the “ALT” key in Windows or the “option” key in macOS. For a same image, changing the bins from 256 to 65536 and establishing the minimum as 0 and the maximum as 65536:

The resulting histogram is not very helpful, because all pixels have intensities that are relatively low and it is so shifted to the left that it is hard to distinguish its shape. We could call again the Histogram

³ Images from “What are Histograms? Analysis & Frequency Distribution | ASQ”, available at <https://asq.org/quality-resources/histogram>, last accessed: Jan 4, 2021.

command but introduce 6765 bins (since the maximum pixel intensity is 6763 for this image) and set the X max as 6765:

Although this is a good option to quickly see the 16-bit histogram of our image stack, we prefer extracting the intensity value of each pixel ourselves and plotting it ourselves to be able to have a 100% control over the raw data and its manipulation for plotting.

To this aim, we have created the ImageJ script "SixteenBitHistogram_ObtainData.ijm" to extract a list of pixel intensity values for the whole image stack, which is stored as the "SixteenBitHistogram_data.csv" file. Then, we use the custom-made MATLAB script "SixteenBitHistogram_PlotData.m" that reads the output and plots it. Both scripts are available as supplementary material.

Run the ImageJ macro. Do not click on any Fiji window while its running. Save the .csv file in the same folder containing the MATLAB script. Run the MATLAB script. We obtain a histogram like the one below (left) and we can easily adjust the axes limits (below right) to see it better.

A screenshot of the scripts is provided below.

```

1 // Ester Comellas
2 // Extract pixel intensity data to plot 16-bit histogram with matlab script
3 // Nov 23, 2020
4
5 // Import the blastema image
6 waitForUser("Load your original image. It must be a tif stack of a 16-bit channel.");
7 rename("original");
8
9 // Create a table with the 16-bit histogram values of each slice
10 nBins = 65535;
11
12 // Define an array with the intensity values
13 // Row numbering starts at 1, but pixel intensity is 0 to nBins=65535
14 intensityvalue = newArray(nBins+1);
15
16 // Print the first column in the table with pixel intensity values
17 for (i=0; i<=nBins; i++){
18   intensityvalue[i] = i;
19   setResult("Intensity value / Slice number", i, intensityvalue[i]);
20 }
21
22 // Loop over all slices
23 for (slice=1; slice<=nSlices; slice++) {
24   if (nSlices>1) run("Set Slice...", "slice=" + slice);
25
26   // Export 16-bit histogram of each slice
27   //run("SixteenBit Histogram");
28
29   // Raw data provides the 16-bit histogram for the current slice
30   // with a bin width = 1, so no information is lost
31   getRawStatistics(nPixels, mean, min, max, std, sliceHist);
32
33   // Print a column in the table for the current slice with pixel intensity counts
34   for (i=0; i<=nBins; i++){
35     if (i<lengthOf(sliceHist)) setResult(slice, i, sliceHist[i]);
36     else setResult(slice, i, 0.0);
37   }
38 }
39 run("Input/Output...", "jpeg=85 gif=-1 file=.csv use_file copy_row save_column");
40
41 // Save the data
42 Dir = getDirectory("Choose a directory to export the results");
43 saveAs("Results", Dir+"SixteenBitHistogram_data.csv");

```

Run Batch Kill persistent Show Errors Clear ▶

The image shows a MATLAB R2019b window titled "MATLAB R2019b - academic use". The main editor window displays a script named "SixteenBitHistogram_PlotData.m" with the following code:

```

1 % Plot 16-bit histogram based on data extracted for each slice
2 % of an image stack using ImageJ macro
3 % Ester Comellas, Nov 2020.
4 clear all;
5 close all;
6
7 %% Read data
8
9 % .csv file produced by ImageJ script.
10 % Columns contain histogram data of a slice (max_num_columns=max_num_slice)
11 % Rows contain num of pixel for each intensity value for a given slice
12 % (max_num_rows=2^16)
13 nbins = 2^16; %Also plots for 8-bit histogram if you change 16-->8 here.
14
15 HistogramSlices = readmatrix('SixteenBitHistogram_data.csv');
16 % Remove header row and first column
17 HistogramSlices(1,:) = [];
18 HistogramStackX = HistogramSlices(:,1);
19 HistogramSlices(:,1) = [];
20
21 % Add data from all slices
22 HistogramStack = sum(HistogramSlices,2);
23
24 % Plot
25 fig1 = figure('Name','SixteenBitHistogram');
26 bar(HistogramStackX,HistogramStack);
27
28 Xlimit = nbins;
29 Ylimit = max(HistogramStack(2:end-1));
30
31 ax = gca;
32 ax.FontSize = 20;
33 ax.XLim = [0,Xlimit];
34 ax.YLim = [0,Ylimit];
35 ax.XLabel.String = 'pixel intensity';
36 ax.YLabel.String = 'number of pixels';
37 set(fig1,'Position',[10, 650, 500, 300]);
38 %saveas(gcf,strcat('results\',Fig1Name, '.png'));
39
40
41
42

```

At the bottom of the window, the Command Window is visible, showing a message: "New to MATLAB? See resources for [Getting Started.](#)" and a prompt "JL >>". The status bar at the bottom indicates "script", "Ln 4", and "Col 11".

3D shape analysis of the humerus

This section corresponds to Fig 1E-H.

We performed the 3D shape analysis with MATLAB. Three separate scripts were generated, to process the data as follows:

- Part 1: 3D limb alignment (Fig 1E)
- Part 2: 2D surface map (heatmap) generation (Fig 1F)
- Part 3: 2D surface map analysis (Fig 1G and H)

We also created the following additional scripts:

- Alternative measures of humerus shaft diameter
- Recovering a humerus surface from mean 2D surface maps

Below is a short description of the contents of each script, but we recommend users to look at the actual scripts, which have been thoroughly commented, for more details.

Part 1: 3D limb alignment

This script orients all limbs such that they are: in the first octant of 3D space, the ends of the radius and ulna point in the positive x-direction, and the ulna is above the radius in the y-direction. The axis of the ulna is then rotated to be parallel to the x-axis in order to align all limbs in the same manner.

The humerus STL, radius STL, ulna STL, ulna eigenvector .txt, and humerus rotation matrix .txt files from the ImageJ segmentation should be placed in a folder named 'input' located within the current file path. Note that the script assumes, based on the output we consistently obtained from BoneJ, that the ulna eigenvector is contained in rows 5-7 of the third column of the .txt file and the humerus rotation matrix is located under the heading 'Rotation Matrix (Source -> Target)' in the corresponding .txt file.

The user must define the following:

- Rotation_z: Set angle of rotation required around the z-axis to have the radius and ulna pointing in the correct direction. Can set as 0 degrees or 180 degrees.
- Rotation_x: Set angle of rotation required around the x-axis to flip the limb upside down. Set as 0 degrees or 180 degrees.
- Reflection_xz: Set as 1 to reflect limb across xz plane or 0 to not reflect. The correct mirroring will result in the ulna being above the radius in the y-direction such that all limbs appear to be left limbs.
- Filename: set a name for the resulting .mat file.
- Savefigure: Set as 0 to inactivate or 1 to activate saving figures in MATLAB's .fig format. Figures generated from the STL surfaces take a long time to save in this file format. It is generally recommended to set savefigure to 0 while running test cases.
- Define the desired colors in RGB for visualizing each bone rudiment.

One may need to run the script and determine from the results if rotation or reflection is required, and then repeat the process. Note that these values must be in accordance with how the image stack was processed in Fiji (e.g. if the image stack of a right limb was already flipped in Fiji, the limb will already appear mirrored here and we should not apply a reflection_xz in MATLAB).

The STL and .txt files from the input folder are automatically read into the MATLAB workspace. A limb alignment matrix is computed combining the humerus rotation matrix, x-axis rotation matrix, z-axis rotation matrix, and reflection matrix (if applicable).

The original bone rudiment surfaces are plotted with the humerus, radius, and ulna STLs designated as pointClouds with the user-assigned colors. The ulna eigenvector is plotted as a line going through the ulna centroid to show the ulna axis.

Then, the original pointClouds are rotated with the limb alignment matrix. Using the x-limits and y-limits of the aligned limb, each limb is translated so that the limb is located in the first octant.

The ulna axis is rotated using the same limb alignment matrix and the ulna centroid is computed for the newly transformed ulna pointCloud. The rotated ulna axis is plotted through the new centroid. The ulna axis is then aligned with the x-axis by finding the angle between the eigenvector and the x-axis. A final rotation matrix with this angle is applied to the ulna axis and entire limb to obtain the final alignment of the whole limb.

The aligned humerus, radius, and ulna pointClouds are then saved in the resulting .mat file.

Part 2: 2D surface map generation

This script fits a cylinder with a hemispherical cap (reference surface) to the humerus surface. Then, a 2D surface map is created using the heatmap function in MATLAB. This 2D representation of the humerus surface normalizes the distance of the humerus surface points to the fitted reference surface. The heatmaps can be aligned based on the ulna centroid position.

The input of this script is the .mat file from Part 1, containing the aligned humerus, radius, and ulna pointClouds. This .mat file should be placed in a folder named 'input'. The user may choose one limb to run through the script or run all of the limbs at once.

This code requires the following community-generated matlab scripts, which are provided with the script, but also available for download from Matlab's File Exchange website:

<https://www.mathworks.com/matlabcentral/fileexchange/>

- trim.m
- cylinderfit.m
- circlefit.m

The user must define the following:

- align: If set to 1, the script will take all existing heatmaps in the results .mat file and align them based on the ulna centroid position. First, one must process all limbs with this parameter set to 0, and then run again setting it to 1.
- runlimb: Either run all limbs by setting it to 'all', or run for a given limb by providing the name exactly as stored in the input .mat file.
- norm_cylinder_height: Define the height of cylindrical part in normalized reference surface ("bullet" shape).
- bin_width: Define the bin width into which the discrete 2D heatmap data points should be group to compute continuous heatmaps.
- bump_trim: To extract the "bumps" from the humerus, indicate how much bump is kept when trimming.
- filename: set a name for the resulting .mat file.
- savefigure: Set as 0 to inactivate or 1 to activate saving figures in MATLAB's .fig format.

The humerus surface is first centered around the origin. Then, the `cylinderfit()` function (obtained from MATLAB File Exchange, and provided with the script) fits a cylinder to the humerus. Note that this function takes a considerable amount of time to run. A hemispherical cap is placed on top to create the reference surface ("bullet shape"), which is then shifted vertically until the top of the hemisphere contacts the humerus surface. The humerus surface with the fitted reference surface is plotted to visually check the fitting is correct. In addition, bone rudiment surfaces of humerus, radius and ulna are plotted with the identified epicondyles as a visual check for the user to ensure the automatic assignment has been done correctly. The identified epicondyles are extracted and shown without the remaining humerus surface. Here, yellow crosses mark the most distal point of each epicondyle, green asterisks mark the centroid of the epicondyles, and a magenta circle identifies the center of the fitted spherical cap. These allow for computation of metrics directly based on the extracted epicondyle surfaces in 3D space, like the angle between epicondyle centroids. Although saved to the results file, we eventually did not use them all to quantify the shape of the humerus in our study.

A heatmap is created on the reference surface, where the colormap correlates to the distance from the reference surface to the experimental humerus surface. Results are shown in a 3D plot. The values of both the heatmap and the reference surface are normalized with the computed fitted cylinder radius, to allow for comparison between limbs. These are also plotted, with the previously computed centroid positions of the "ulna bump" (dorsal epicondyle) and "radius bump" (ventral epicondyle) projected onto the reference surface. To flatten out the heatmap from the reference surface into a 2D surface map representation, we make use of coordinate transformation functions in MATLAB (transformation between spherical or polar coordinates to Cartesian coordinates). We then convert the 2D surface point representation to a continuous surface map by grouping the data points into bins, and averaging their value for each bin. We plot the original 2D surface point heatmap, the bin count map (to visualize the data distribution used to compute the continuous heatmap), and the final continuous 2D surface representation. Black bins indicate lack of data for that bin (NaN = not a number). Many humeri will have empty rows in the bottom (proximal) part of the 2D surface map. This means that the segmented humerus was shorter than the selected normalized cylinder height.

In MATLAB, the flattened continuous heatmap is stored as a matrix, in which the rows of the matrix correspond to the columns of the heatmap and the columns of the matrix correspond to the rows of the heatmap. Each point in the matrix contains a value that represents the normalized humerus surface distance. If the user has chosen to align the heatmaps, the heatmaps will be aligned such that each heatmap's ulna centroid will be located in the same column. The ulna centroid from each ulna pointCloud is converted to a "heatmap bin" location. Then, the heatmap with the right-most ulna centroid is found, whose centroid column will be used as basis for alignment of all other heatmaps. Each heatmap will shift columns from the right-side to the left-side of the heatmap by the appropriate number of columns such that each heatmap's ulna centroid is located in the same column. For each limb, a separate heatmap is created in which the ulna centroid is plotted in black to visually confirm that the shifting has been computed correctly. This separate heatmap is not used for any further calculations.

The resulting .mat file contains the metrics computed from the extracted epicondyle point clouds as well as the 2D continuous heatmaps or surface maps. The bin size used to compute the continuous heatmap and the cylinder height used to create the reference surface are also stored. If they have been computed, the aligned maps are also saved.

Part 3: 2D surface map analysis

This script extracts the humeri epicondyles (red areas) and concavities (blue areas) from the 2D surface maps created in Part 2. Then the area, volume and bounding box dimensions of the extracted

shapes are computed as a means of quantifying humeri shape. Once all limbs have been processed, a statistical analysis on the computed metrics can be performed.

The input of this script is the .mat file from Part 2, containing the 2D surface maps (which may be aligned or not). This .mat file should be placed in a folder named 'input'. The user may choose one limb to run through the script or run all of the limbs at once.

This code requires the following community-generated matlab scripts, which are provided with the script, but also available for download from Matlab's File Exchange website:

<https://www.mathworks.com/matlabcentral/fileexchange/>

- swtest.m
- distinguishable_colors.m

The user must define the following:

- runlimb: Either run all limbs by setting it to 'all', or run for a given limb by providing the name exactly as stored in the input .mat file. Once all 2D surface maps have been processed and the user only is interested in running the statistical analysis, it can be set to 'none'.
- aligneddata: If set to 1, the script will use the existing aligned heatmaps in the results .mat file, otherwise it will use the non-aligned 2D heatmaps.
- runboxplots: Set to 1 to perform the statistical analysis on the computed metrics and plot the results. When only interested in extracting metrics from the 2D surface maps, set to 0.
- colorbar_limit: Limits of the colorbar legend of the 2D surface map and all subsequent plots used in the data processing.
- contour_incr: Increment used in the contour map created from the 2D surface map, which is used as basis for extracting the epicondyle and concavity shapes.
- contour_pos_area: Contour limit used to extract the epicondyle shapes. Normalized distances to the reference surface above this value will be extracted and analyzed as epicondyles.
- contour_neg_area: Contour limit used to extract the concavity shapes. Normalized distances to the reference surface below this value will be extracted and analyzed as concavities.
- Filename: set a name for the resulting .mat file.
- savefigure: Set as 0 to inactivate or 1 to activate saving figures in MATLAB's .fig format.

Note that this script generates many intermediate plots. These are not displayed on screen. Instead, they're directly saved as a png file in the corresponding limb subfolder within the results folder.

First, the left half of the 2D surface map is duplicated on the right side of the 2D surface map. This is to ensure concavities are not split in half and can be analyzed correctly. We had to manually adjust the limits for duplication for some of the 2D surface maps. Also, in specific limbs with segmentation artifacts (which appear as blue zones in the proximal portion of the 2D surface map) we remove the bottom rows of the 2D surface maps. Next, empty bins of the map are "filled in" using the MATLAB fillmissing() function and linear interpolation between neighboring bin values.

A contour map is created based on the processed 2D surface map using the MATLAB contour() function to plot. We then plot the contour lines of the epicondyle and concavity areas, based on the values (contour_pos_area and contour_neg_area, respectively) introduced by the user. This serves as a visual check for the user to ensure the shapes are being detected correctly. Often, contour lines outside the actual epicondyles and/or concavities will appear, typically in the proximal part of the humerus (bottom part of the 2D contour map). The script automatically identifies the two largest epicondyle and concavity areas for analysis. A plot is provided where all the areas identified by the script are shown. The user should check them to ensure the automatic selection worked correctly. Otherwise, either manual modification of the code would be needed to override the automatic

selection or adjusting the initial point for duplication of the left part of the 2D surface map, to ensure the concavities and/or epicondyles are not split in half.

Finally, the normalized area, normalized volume, centroid and box size (x and y dimensions) of each extracted shape (2 epicondyles and 2 concavities) is computed. The normalized volume corresponds to the volume of the contour map above/below the contour limit used to extract the epicondyle/concavity. It is computed by multiplying the area of each bin times the normalized distance from the limiting contour to the actual intensity value at that bin, and then summing up for all bins within the shape being analyzed.

Once all limbs have been processed, the user can select `runboxplots=1` to run a statistical analysis on the computed metrics. For each measurement, data is tested for normality using different tests (Jarque-Bera, Anderson-Darling, Lilliefors and Shapiro-Wilk). If data is normally distributed according to a given test, the value in table = 0. The normal probability plots are also provided. We perform normality computations for the DMSO and GSK groups separately, and for the SUM of all data points, i.e., for the two groups together. The corresponding p-value for each is also provided in the table. In our study, we used the value provided under "SUM" for the "Shapiro-Wilk" normality test. If this was 0, then we used the one-way ANOVA to test for significance, if it was 1, we used the Kruskal-Wallis test instead. The table also provides results for a two-sample t-test and a Wilcoxon rank sum test. Finally, boxplots with the individual data points superimposed are computed for all metrics analyzed, and the p-value obtained as well as the test used are given in the title of each plot.

Alternative measures of humerus shaft diameter

HumerusDiameter.m determines additional metrics of the humerus shaft to confirm that the DMSO and GSK groups do not present statistically significant differences in the humerus shaft fitted diameters. The resulting .mat files from the Part 1 and Part 2 scripts should be located in the current filepath.

The user must define the following:

- `proportion_top`: Factor of the fitted diameter that will be used to compute the length to trim off from the top (distal end) of the humerus in order to extract the humerus shaft. A value of 2 indicates $2 \times \text{fitted_diameter}$ will be trimmed from the top.
- `proportion_bottom`: Factor of the fitted diameter that will be used to compute the length of shaft to keep from the top of the trimmed humerus. A value of 0.5 indicates that the extracted shaft will be $0.5 \times \text{fitted_diameter}$ in height, from the most distal part after trimming off the top.
- `sliceThickness`: slice thickness (in microns) of the slices that the shaft should be divided into for the analysis.
- `filename`: File name for the .mat results file.
- `plotfigures`: Set this to 0 to turn off figures of each individual pointcloud slice section or set to 1 to show these figures. If set to 0, figures of the whole humerus shaft are still shown.

First, the humerus pointCloud and fitted diameter (given from the .mat files from Part 1 and Part 2, respectively) for each limb are matched based on the limb names. Points in the pointCloud with a z-position above the trim value computed with `proportion_top` are removed, with the goal of removing the humerus epicondyles. Then, the points below a certain distance computed with `proportion_bottom` are used to remove the segmentation edge artifacts on the bottom of the shaft. The resulting pointCloud is the humerus trimmed shaft.

Each limb's trimmed shaft is divided into 'slices' of the thickness defined by `sliceThickness`. Each slice is projected on the x-y plane and a binary image of the resulting shape is created. Using the binary image, the MATLAB function `regionprops()` computes the following shape metrics: area,

EquivDiameter (the diameter of a circle with an equivalent area of the shape), major axis, minor axis, circumference, and the major/minor axis length difference. This process is repeated for each slice, then the average of each metric for all of the slices is computed and stored for each limb. This process will repeat for each limb.

The resulting .mat file contains the averaged metrics for each limb's trimmed shaft, which can then be processed following a statistical analysis similar to that provided in Part 3. The MATLAB script used to compute these boxplots and the others presented in the study is provided with this tutorial.

Computing mean 2D surface maps and recovering the humerus surface

This script computes the mean 2D surface maps for the DMSO and GSK groups based on the aligned individual 2D surface maps of the individual limbs resulting from Part 2. A mean humerus surface is then recovered for each group and they are superimposed in 3D space for visual comparison. It serves to confirm that our 2D surface maps contain all the information needed to recover the 3D humerus surface they represent.

The user must define the following:

- `colorbar_limit`: Limits of the colorbar legend of the 2D surface map and all subsequent plots used in the data processing.
- `norm_cylinder_height`: Define the height of cylindrical part in normalized reference surface ("bullet" shape).
- `bin_width`: Width of the bins in the heatmaps, used in extracting the discrete points to reconstruct the map on the reference surface.
- `visible`: Show figures on screen ('on') or not ('off'). Figures are always saved to png files.
- `scaling_radius`: Radius used to reconstruct the mean humeri surfaces from the corresponding normalized surface maps.

Using the aligned heatmaps, a mean heatmap is computed for both groups by averaging the intensities in each bin from each group limb's heatmaps. Because of segmentation artifacts in some limbs, the mean heatmaps show unrealistic horizontal stripes towards the proximal (bottom) part. We remove the artifacts from the original individual heatmaps and compute the means again. Next, we convert the mean heatmap to a discrete 2D surfacemap by extracting a data point with the intensity of each bin. Following the inverse procedure to that used in Part 2, we map the 2D surface map of discrete points onto the normalized reference surface ("bullet" shape) using coordinate transformations. Then, a mean humerus surface is created for each group based on the intensity value of each point. We plot the recovered surface and the corresponding reference surface map together for the DMSO and GSK groups separately. Finally, we plot the mean DMSO and GSK surfaces together, scaled with the provided `scaling_radius`.

EdU+ cell analysis of the humerus

This section corresponds to Fig 1I-K.

To identify and count the EdU positive cells within the humeri in our 3D image stacks, we combined Fiji, Stardist and MATLAB to create a processing pipeline, outlined in this scheme:

Pre-Processing

Importing Images

First, images can be opened in Fiji using the Bio-Formats Importer (*Plugins -> Bio-Formats -> Bio-Formats Importer*). Images can also be opened by dragging their file onto the Fiji window but opening in Bio-Formats ensures no metadata is lost when doing so.

The Bio-Formats Importer will open up with options in an additional window. Here you can explore various options. Some notable options include *Display metadata* which will display image information

and metadata and *Use virtual stack* which will allow you to open just part of the image stack and only render relevant substacks of the image stack (useful if your computer has memory issues but sometimes problematic as certain commands that affect the whole stack cannot be used without loading in the whole image). Hit *OK* to open the image.

Adjusting Brightness and Contrast

Once the image is open, it may appear blank/black. To fix this and see the image, run the command *Brightness/Contrast*. All commands can be searched for in the main Fiji window which is far easier than using the menu directories. Once you run *Brightness/Contrast*, you'll be able to adjust the viewable intensities of the image. To get a relatively balanced view of the image, scroll to the middle of the image stack, click *Auto* and *Apply*.

Cropping the Initial Image

An initial crop is helpful to restrict analysis to the relevant part of the image. This can be done by running the *Crop (3D)* command. There are many crop commands available in Fiji all of which have slightly different applications and advantages. *Crop (3D)* is used here since it allows you to input

specific values to crop an image instead of making a selection as you would if you used the *Crop* tool. This allows more specific and exact cropping. When running *Crop (3D)*, a window will prompt you to confirm. Uncheck *Three pane view?* and click *OK*.

Next, the *Crop Options* window will appear. You are able to insert the boundaries of the image you would like to crop out of the original image. In accordance with most image analysis tool standards, X coordinates increase from left to right while Y coordinates increase from top to bottom. As you fill in the boundaries for your crop, you can hit *Set from fields above* and the purple outline around your image will update to show the location being cropped out.

It's important to scroll through the whole image to ensure your crop does not cut off any part of the region of interest. It's far better to crop too little than too much. If you are having difficulty with this, it may be worth looking at the three pane view enabled in the previous step. Once you have found the correct boundaries you would like to crop within, make sure to record the values in a lab notebook or other notetaking resource, click *Set from fields above*, and then click *Crop*.

Background Subtraction

The background of the image can be subtracted to increase contrast for the objects of interest in your image. To do this, run the command *Subtract Background*. Similar to other commands, a window will appear allowing you to set the exact parameters of the subtraction.

Note: *Rolling ball radius* represents the size of the sphere (in pixels) around each pixel that will be used to determine the average intensity around every given pixel. In short, *Rolling ball radius* is a parameter to determine the locality of the background subtract. It's recommended to have a *Rolling ball radius* no smaller than the largest object of interest in your image. To find this, simply scroll through your image and find one of the largest objects and measure its diameter using the selection tool. Since you may not have the exact biggest object, make your *Rolling ball radius* slightly higher than what you measure to ensure no data is lost. It's better to have a less than ideal background subtract than to lose data.

Macro: Image Tiling

Next, the image can be cropped into equal size tiles using the *ImageStack_Tile_Crop* macro provided. The script can be opened by dragging and dropping it onto the main Fiji window. It is not necessary to use *Bio-Imports* when loading macros. To use the macro, input the file path you would like to save the tiles to and click *Run*.

```

24 // User input number of divisions
25 #@ int(label="How many divisions?") n
26 #@ Boolean(label="Close image when done?") b
27 #@ Boolean(label="Check tile sizes? (Won't run divisions)") q
28
29 // INPUT FILEPATH FOR SAVING DESTINATION
30 filePath = "C:/Users/giona/OneDrive/Documents/Research/Macro Output/"
31
32 // get basic image info

```


Once opened, the macro will prompt the user for a number of divisions, whether to close the image, and whether to check tile sizes. The first time you run the script on an image, check the *Check tile sizes? (Won't run divisions)* box and then click *OK*. Doing so will prevent the script from actually cropping the image and instead display a new *Log* window with the tile sizes that will result from each division. A good number of divisions is the smallest number of divisions such that both the Tile Width, and Tile Height are less than or very close to 300 pixels. In the case shown below, 3 divisions is shown to produce tiles with a Tile Width of 201 pixels and a Tile Height of 301 pixels. Since both dimensions are far below, or close to 300 pixels, 3 divisions should be used.

To tile the original image, make sure to click the window containing the image in order to select it then click *Run* again. When the macro window comes up again, uncheck the *Check tile sizes?* box, input the number of divisions, and click *OK*. You can optionally elect to close the parent image when done but this is not necessary. Once the script finishes running, you will find the cropped tiles of the parent image in the folder you designated as *filePath*. The tile position of each image is shown at the end of the filename in brackets. Make sure to record the number of divisions.

Training Model

Creating a Training Set

To create a training set for Stardist, you will need to first crop out various $256 \times 256 \times 16$ pixel substacks from your dataset (see *Cropping the Initial Image* in *Pre-Processing*). It's important to select these substacks with variability such that together they represent the entire dataset accurately. These substacks are used to train the model so any specific patterns in your dataset that are not represented in the training set will not be recognized by the trained model.

Each training stack cropped out must have a corresponding labeled stack created as well. This can be done in Fiji. First, open the training stack and adjust the brightness so it is visible. After that, the polygon (free form) selection tool can be used to trace each cell.

Once a cell is traced, hit 'T' to add it to the *ROI Manager*. Once all cells in the current slice are added to the *ROI Manager*, run the *ROI Map* function (installed via the LOCI plugin) which will turn the selections into an ROI Map.

Repeat this process to create an ROI map for each slice of the training stack and then run the *Concatenate* command with all of them open to create a labeled image stack. You will need to create a labeled image stack for each training stack in the training set.

After you have created enough training sets (extremely variable based on how hard your images are to train on / how varied they are although a rough estimate would be 15 pairs), create and upload two folders to Google Drive. The first folder should contain the training image stacks and the second folder should contain their corresponding labeled data.

Important: Each labeled image stack should have the EXACT same filename as its corresponding training stack in order to be used by Stardist.

Training Model in Stardist

The ZeroCostDL4Mic notebook can be obtained at:

<https://github.com/HenriquesLab/ZeroCostDL4Mic/wiki>

To open the 3D notebook, click *Open In Colab*. There is also a 2D notebook that can be accessed here as well.

StarDist (2D)	here and here	Nuclei segmentation	here	
StarDist (3D)	here and here	Nuclei segmentation	from Stardist github	

Once open, you'll be able to navigate through the notebook. The notebook functions as a tutorial of its own explaining parameters and walking you through each cell. For clarity, the most important parts will be explained here as well.

Note: the notebook is constantly changing so some sections may change names or have different parameters. If there is a discrepancy between this tutorial and the notebook, refer to the notebook. **We recommend carefully reading the StarDist notebook instructions as you advance through this tutorial.**

First, run sections *1. Install StarDist and dependencies* and *2. Initialise the Colab session*. These sections set up the notebook and the colab environment. Once they have run, refer to section *3. Select your parameters and paths*. In this section, you'll input the following data

Training_source: the file path to the google drive folder containing your original images in the training set

Training_target: the file path containing the ROI Maps manually created for the training set

model_name: The name you want the model to have when it is trained

model_path: The file path you would like to save the model to

number_of_epochs: The number of iterations of training you would like to use (recommended 400)

Default advanced parameters can be used: on a case by case basis, some of the parameters can be changed depending on the images being used and the size of the training set. All parameters are described in the notebook in depth.

▶ Path to training images:

Training_source: "Insert text here" "

Training_target: "Insert text here" "

Name of the model and path to model folder:

model_name: "Insert text here" "

model_path: "Insert text here" "

Other parameters for training:

number_of_epochs: 200

Advanced Parameters

Use_Default_Advanced_Parameters:

Data augmentation can be enabled after setting the training parameters by running the data augmentation cell. This will dramatically increase the size of the training set by rotating, reflecting, and distorting each image pair in the training set. It is recommended to use data augmentation if your training set has less than 100 element pairs.

▶ Use_Data_augmentation:

[Show code](#)

Next, section 4. *Train the Network* can be run and will take anywhere from 1-12 hours. Once this section is completed, the trained model will be available to use in the designated model folder.

Processing

Generating Predictions in Stardist

In contrast to training a model, generating predictions in Stardist is relatively straightforward. First, upload all tiles that you would like to generate predictions for to a Google Drive folder. Open up the Stardist notebook once again and run sections 1. *Install StarDist and dependencies* and 2. *Initialise the Colab session* again. Navigate to the section marked 6.1. *Generate prediction(s) from unseen dataset*. In this section, copy the file path of your Google Drive folder containing the tiled image stacks to the *Data_Folder* field as well as the file path of a Google Drive folder you would like to save the predictions to in *Results_Folder*. If you have rerun the notebook since training a model, leave the *Use_the_current_trained_model* box unchecked and input the file path of the trained model's folder to *Prediction_model_folder*.

Note: we provide our trained Stardist model with this tutorial. Unzip the compressed file "*trained-Stardist-model_EdUNucleiModel.zip*" and upload the folder and all its contents as is to your Google Drive. Then, indicate the path to this folder instead.

Provide the path to your dataset and to the folder where the prediction will be saved (Result folder), then play the cell to predict output on your unseen images.

Data_folder: "Insert text here"

Results_folder: "Insert text here"

Do you want to use the current trained model?

Use_the_current_trained_model:

If not, please provide the path to the model folder:

Prediction_model_folder: "Insert text here"

Once you have filled in all the fields, run the cell. After all predictions have been generated, the cell will stop running and you can download all the predictions from the results folder to your local computer for post-processing.

Post-Processing

Macro: Generating Statistics on Prediction Images

The next step requires corresponding the cropped humerus mask for each prediction image. Corresponding humerus mask for each original image should be imported, cropped, and tiled using the same parameters that were recorded for each parent image stack. Two folders should be created; one containing the prediction images downloaded from Google Drive and the other containing the corresponding mask images for each tile. Filenames should be similar so that if both folders were sorted by name, the masks would be in the same order as their corresponding prediction tiles.

Next, the BatchProcess_3DObjectCounter macro can be run. Similar to other macros, the macro can be opened by dragging it onto the main Fiji window. Once open, the file path to save results in can be designated under *filePath*. Run the script by clicking *Run*.

Note: This macro was developed in a WinOS. If you run it in macOS, all slashes in file paths must be changed from "\\" to "/" for the script to run correctly. Check code lines 26, 48, 49 and 61.

```

20 // get input and output directories
21 #@ File (label = "Input directory", style = "directory") input
22 #@ File (label = "Mask directory", style = "directory") input2
23 #@ String (label = "File suffix", value = ".tif") suffix
24 #@ Boolean(label="Is pixel intensity of mask 255 instead of 1?") b // is pixel intensity 255?
25
26 filePath = "C:\\Users\\giona\\OneDrive\\Documents\\Research\\MacroOutput2\\";
27
28 processFolder(input, input2); // process entirety of both folders
29
30 // function to scan folders/subfolders/files to find files with correct suffix

```

Run Batch Kill persistent

Once the script is running, a second window will be created requesting the input directories for predictions and masks. Click *Browse* to locate the folders. If running the script multiple times, make sure to click *Browse* even if the correct directory appears to be selected. This is because the folder contents are only updated when the folder is selected. You can also supply the file type of your images although this will be .tif in most cases. If masks contain a pixel intensity of 255, make sure to check the corresponding box so the script can handle it accordingly.

Results from running *3D Objects Counter* on each masked image will be saved as Excel files to the location specified by *filePath*.

Note: Stardist provides image stacks with masks in which the resolution is 1 pixel in all directions, as shown below (comparison of the original image stack input in Stardist, left, and the predictions produced, right). The macro updates this information in the image stack containing cell nuclei masks, by copying the pixel width, height and depth from the original image into the masks image, before running *3D Objects Counter* on it. Then, the volumes of the identified objects will be provided in micrometers cubed. However, the position of their center of mass is given in pixels.

Script: Generating 3D Plots and Obtaining Cell Count by Concatenating Tiles

Once all Excel files have been saved into the designated folder, the results need to be combined into full images. This is done using the *MATLABCellPlotter* script. A folder named "input" must be created containing the following:

- All the excel files from *3D Objects counter*
- The text file for each original image specifying their rotation matrix (obtained in Part 1 of the 3D shape analysis)

The following information is input manually by the user:

- *cutoffHeight*: Distance from the distal tip to cut off the cell count in the humeri.
- *lowVolume*: Lower threshold for the cell volume cut off.

- *highVolume*: Upper threshold for the cell volume cut off.
- *XY_res, Z_res*: pixel and voxel resolution of the original image.
- *rotation_z, rotation_x*: Rotation angles used in Part 1 of 3D shape analysis to align each limb.
- *reflection_xz*: Indicate whether reflection was used in Part 1 of 3D shape analysis to align each limb.
- *limb_num*: 0 indicates all limbs should be processed, if a single limb from the list provided in the script is to be processed, indicate the specific number.
- *savefigure*: Set as 0 to inactivate or 1 to activate saving figures in MATLAB's .fig format.

The script reads in the Center of Mass (CoM) and Volumes of each identified object from the .csv files in the input folder. CoM values must be converted into microns using the pixel and voxel resolution values provided by the user (*XY_res, Z_res*). Then, it adjusts the CoM positions through translation of the coordinates, based on each individual tile position. Finally it groups all the objects together and applies the appropriate rotation matrix to align the objects according to the alignment of the humerus mask performed in Part 1 of the 3D shape analysis. Objects with volume values above and below the given thresholds (*highVolume* and *lowVolume*, respectively) are removed as well as objects beyond the defined distance *cutoffHeight*.

Plots will be generated for each limb showing all the CoM identified by 3D Objects Counter, with the point size proportional to the object volume, along with the total cell nuclei count recorded. Another plot of the 3D position of the identified objects is provided, where only the cells remaining after applying the volume threshold and hard cut-off distance are shown. Here, both point size and color are correlated with object volume. The lightest and darkest shade of orange correspond to the minimum and maximum volume sizes within the limb. Additional information is displayed in the command window for each limb.

Note: The script takes a while to run depending on the number of humeri.

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